

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.8 RRI PROJECT REPORT

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Executive summary

The AquaWind project has applied the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework throughout its lifecycle, assessed in two audits using the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) across all Work Packages. The 1st audit established a strong baseline, identifying opportunities in data harmonisation, gender integration, and stakeholder feedback. The 2nd audit confirmed continued progress in these areas, with improved open access practices, sustained gender balance, strengthened ethical compliance, broader stakeholder engagement, and enhanced science education resources. This trajectory demonstrates the consortium's commitment to embedding RRI principles in both technical and societal dimensions of the project.

1. Introduction

The AquaWind project aims to advance innovative solutions in marine renewable energy, with a strong focus on sustainability, environmental responsibility, and community engagement. As part of our commitment to excellence, the project integrates **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** principles across all work packages (WPs). These principles serve as a framework to ensure that the research process and its outcomes are inclusive, transparent, and aligned with societal values.

The RRI framework emphasizes key dimensions such as **Open Access, Gender Equality, Ethics and Research Integrity, Stakeholder Engagement, and Science Education**. By addressing these dimensions, AquaWind seeks to promote collaboration between stakeholders, enhance ethical and inclusive research practices, and maximize the positive impact of its findings.

This report presents the results of the RRI self-assessment for the two reporting periods during the project lifespan, which involved input from all WP leaders through a structured Self-Assessment Tool (SAT). The purpose of this assessment is to evaluate the progress made in implementing RRI principles and to identify areas for improvement as the project advances.

Through this report, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the RRI efforts across all WPs, highlighting achievements, challenges, and actionable recommendations.

2. Methodology

The methodology for the RRI assessment of the AquaWind project was designed to systematically evaluate the integration of RRI principles across all Work Packages (WPs). The process leveraged a structured SAT and involved collaboration with WP leaders to gather data on their respective activities. The SAT template was developed by Task 7.6 Leader PLOCAN, with the feedback of the WP7 Leader and project partners. For the design of the SAT, PLOCAN brings in previous experience in RRI assessment from the EU H2020 MUSICA project.

Below is an outline of the approach used:

1. Framework Definition

The assessment was based on the key dimensions of RRI as defined by the European Commission:

- **Open Access**
- **Gender Equality**
- **Ethics and Research Integrity**
- **Stakeholder Engagement**
- **Science Education**

These dimensions provided the foundation for evaluating the alignment of AquaWind's activities with RRI principles.

2. Development of the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT)

The SAT was designed to collect concise, focused responses from WP leaders on specific questions related to each RRI dimension. It consisted of:

- **Open-ended questions:** To capture qualitative insights.
- **Work conducted and planned:** Each question required a summary of work completed during the reporting period and planned activities for the next phase.

3. Data Collection

- **WP Leader Participation:** Each WP leader completed the SAT for their respective work packages. The tool was distributed digitally, ensuring accessibility and ease of use.
- **Period of Assessment:** Data collection focused on the activities conducted during the two reporting periods.
 - **1st Period of Assessment:** 1/09/2022-31/10/2024
 - **2nd Period of Assessment:** 1/11/2024-1/08/2025

4. Data Compilation and Analysis

- **Compilation:** Responses from the SAT were aggregated into a centralized database for analysis.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Key themes, achievements, and challenges were identified from narrative responses.

5. Validation

- **Cross-checking:** The responses were reviewed to ensure accuracy and consistency.
- **Feedback Loop:** WP leaders were consulted to clarify ambiguities and provide additional context where needed.

6. Work Package leaders

Work Package	Title	Leader	Involved members in deliverables
WP1	Setting legal and social conditions	PLOCAN	ENEROCEAN, CMC, WAVEC
WP2	W2Power prototype upgrade procedures and designs, harbourside works	ENEROCEAN	GOBCAN
WP3	Aquaculture system: Design and harbourside	ULPGC	

	aquaculture trials.		
WP4	Pilot Demonstration Stage at offshore test site; Monitoring and O&M, environmental impact	GOBCAN	ULPGC, WAVEC
WP5	Exploitation: Business plans, Sustainability Plans and Knowledge transfer & IP	PLOCAN	CE
WP6	Project Coordination and Management	GOBCAN	CE
WP7	Dissemination and Communication, RRI, Public engagement	CE	PLOCAN

3. Result by RRI Dimension

3.1. Open Access

Open Access (OA) practices have been a central element of the AquaWind project, ensuring transparency, accessibility, and compliance with Horizon Europe requirements. Across all Work Packages (WPs), the consortium demonstrated clear progress between the 1st and 2nd audits, moving from initial planning and set-up to the implementation of more structured OA mechanisms.

Work Package 1:

During the 1st audit, WP1 ensured that all public deliverables and datasets were openly accessible, primarily via Zenodo, with DOIs provided for traceability. The team committed to publish findings in open-access journals and aligned with AquaWind's policy to increase the proportion of open-access outputs up to 75%. A comprehensive data management plan was also in place, with updates foreseen to ensure compliance with FAIR principles.

By the 2nd audit, findings were published in Zenodo and made deliverables openly available on both Zenodo and the project website. Accessibility was maintained through continuous uploading of datasets and documentation, with DOIs ensuring tracking. The data management plan was updated for WP1, further reinforcing open-access practices and transparency.

Work Package 2:

In the 1st audit, during this period it was reported that while some outputs were sensitive due to intellectual property issues, non-confidential results were shared in open events like the Showcase Project Event and in publications by WP7 such as website news or promotional videos. Initial activities and results, particularly regarding the new design of the W2Power prototype and aquaculture equipment, had already been presented at scientific events. WP2 relied on WP6's Data Management Plan for coordination and committed to evaluating which data could be made publicly available.

By the 2nd audit, WP2 continued to follow this approach, sharing non-IP-sensitive information through scientific publications, conferences, and project events. Additional dissemination was achieved via newsletters and presentations, ensuring visibility of relevant outputs. The data management plan was periodically revised to identify potential updates or inclusion of new datasets, consolidating WP2's contribution to AquaWind's open-access strategy while protecting sensitive results.

Work Package 3:

For the 1st audit, WP3 reported that, despite IP-sensitive deliverables, some results—particularly from the harbourside aquaculture trials—were to be published in open-access peer-reviewed journals. Activities and results had already been presented at the Spanish National Aquaculture Congress 2024, and a ULPGC master’s thesis stemmed from WP3. Plans included preparing Q1-level publications and presenting additional posters/abstracts to scientific congresses in order to further present outcomes of D3.3.

By the 2nd audit, WP3 had further advanced in preparing a Q1 peer-reviewed publication and presented new abstracts. The team developed a clearer overview of which results could be openly shared and coordinated with WP5 to address IP issues. Two posters on WP3 public results are in the pipeline, and they will be presented at the EU Aquaculture Congress in September 2025, strengthening WP3’s contribution to open-access knowledge sharing.

Work Package 4:

During the 1st audit, WP4 focused on the demonstration pilots of the AquaWind multi-use prototype. Although some deliverables (e.g. D4.1) were sensitive, three out of four were public and planned for open-access release upon EC approval. Results from testing and impact evaluation were expected to feed peer-reviewed publications and dissemination activities such as the Final Conference.

By the 2nd audit, WP4 had extended its pilot activities and, while results were still being collected, the consortium prepared to release deliverables (D4.2, D4.3, D4.4) as open-access outputs before project closure. A final survey was also planned to collect stakeholder perceptions. WP4 continued assessing IP-sensitive versus open-access data, ensuring that once pilots were finalised, results would be openly shared in line with EC requirements.

Work Package 5:

In the 1st audit, WP5 committed to publishing findings in open-access journals and making public deliverables and datasets available through Zenodo and the project website. The team followed a clear data management plan, updated to meet FAIR standards. Plans included increasing open-access publications to 75% of outputs.

By the 2nd audit, WP5 had successfully published findings through Zenodo and made deliverables accessible online. The data management plan had been revised to integrate additional datasets, maintaining compliance with AquaWind’s open-access policy.

Work Package 6:

At the 1st audit, WP6 ensured that public deliverables from across the consortium were made available via the AquaWind website and open-access platforms such as Zenodo, while WP6's own deliverables remained sensitive due to financial and management content. Task 6.5 guaranteed proper data handling and GDPR compliance, with plans to strengthen coordination with WP7 to promote wider dissemination. A data management plan was also developed defining key datasets for the project, and these were periodically revised by the Steering Committee members.

By the 2nd audit, WP6 continued this coordination role, ensuring regular publication of approved deliverables through Zenodo and the website, while supporting WP7 in promoting results through digital channels. The data management plan remained valid and effective, updated where necessary to reflect new datasets.

Work Package 7:

During the 1st audit, focus was on communication and dissemination, ensuring that all public results and deliverables from technical WPs were made openly available. Together with WP6, it guaranteed that EC-approved outputs were uploaded to the AquaWind website and Zenodo. Initial results were shared through abstracts and conference papers, while WP7 also managed promotion through social media, newsletters, press releases, and events. A KPI for scientific publications was embedded in the Grant Agreement, with the 1st steps toward dedicated publications beginning. Planned actions included coordinating with partners to prepare peer-reviewed articles and continuing the wide dissemination of public results while safeguarding sensitive information under GDPR.

By the 2nd audit, the initial approach was kept, ensuring continuous promotion of project activities and results across multiple channels, from digital tools (social media, website, newsletters, video campaigns) to onsite events and press releases. It supported the dissemination of publications and abstracts stemming from other WPs, such as WP3's results presented at the Spanish National Aquaculture Congress. WP7 also continued implementing the Data Management Plan through WP6, ensuring compliance with GDPR and consistent availability of data via recognized open-access platforms.

3.2. GENDER EQUALITY

Gender Equality (GE) was integrated across AquaWind as part of its RRI framework, with the consortium showing increasing awareness and concrete actions between the 1st and 2nd audits. While not all technical activities are directly linked to gender considerations, all WPs acknowledged the importance of balanced participation and inclusivity, progressively embedding gender-sensitive practices. It is also worth noting that a dedicated task on gender auditing was included in WP6 and an associated report has been delivered (D6.5 Report on gender and diversity principles).

Work Package 1:

During the 1st audit, WP1 identified the underrepresentation of women in technical and engineering positions as the main issue to address. To mitigate this, PLOCAN set recruitment targets and implemented an internal mentorship programme where senior female researchers mentored early-career women and other underrepresented genders. Gender balance was promoted in both research teams and leadership positions, while methodologies were refined to include gender-specific data collection and analysis. Planned actions focused on reviewing hiring and promotion policies to increase representation in leadership roles to at least 50% in the next phase and continuing the internal mentorship program.

By the 2nd audit, it was maintained its efforts, ensuring continuity in gender representation within the project team. No major changes occurred in team composition, but the internal mentorship program continued to be applied. While no new methodological refinements were introduced during this stage, WP1 confirmed ongoing commitment to gender equality in recruitment, leadership roles, and decision-making processes, with a steady balance achieved across the team.

Work Package 2:

During the 1st audit, WP2, led by EnerOcean, highlighted its strong foundations in gender equality, as the company maintains 50% female participation in management and has an equality protocol eliminating discrimination. Within WP2's technical team, four out of twelve members were women (33%). As also reported in D6.5, good gender balance was ensured in both technicians and researchers from partner organisations, with fair participation promoted based on technical merit. Gender dimension was also integrated into activities related to the upgrade of the W2Power prototype, where female and male technicians were equally engaged. Planned actions included

maintaining fair gender representation and supporting project partners in equality initiatives.

By the 2nd audit, WP2 had fully finalised its activities, maintaining as much as possible a fair gender balance. The WP engaged female representatives in the Steering Committee and Management Board to review final results and deliverables. Although WP2 concluded, its contribution to gender equality was acknowledged through balanced involvement across roles and technical activities, as well as recommendations captured in the Dissemination & Communication Plan and the Project Management Plan.

Work Package 3:

During the 1st audit, WP3 identified a potential issue with the underrepresentation of female researchers in the ULPGC aquaculture team. However, a fair balance between male and female researchers and technicians from partner organisations was ensured in practice. WP3 activities, being highly technical and linked to the design and testing of the aquaculture system combined with offshore wind energy, successfully integrated contributions from both genders. The gender dimension was embedded in the methodology by involving diverse profiles in technical activities, even though participation was based on technical merits. No mentorship or specific gender support programmes were reported within WP3.

By the 2nd audit, WP3 had already concluded. As such, no new gender-specific activities were undertaken. The gender balance achieved during its operation was maintained until closure, and the gender dimension could still be considered when preparing scientific publications based on WP3 results.

Work Package 4:

In the 1st audit, WP4, coordinated by GOBCAN-ACIISI, was reported a balanced representation of male and female responsible managers within its core team. Across project partners, technical staff and project managers involved in WP4 also ensured fair representation. The Steering Committee (SC), where WP4 deliverables and outputs were reviewed, played a key role in ensuring inclusiveness and gender balance in leadership and decision-making. WP4's technical activities, relating to the testing of the multi-use prototype, also incorporated gender dimension through the involvement of both male and female staff in pilot activities. In addition, Task 1.4 foresees the implementation of a post-demonstration survey that will explicitly collect perceptions from both male and female stakeholder groups.

By the 2nd audit, WP4 maintained this fair representation of male and female staff. The same approach was applied in terms of decision-making and participation. The post-demonstration survey remained a key mechanism for integrating the gender dimension into WP4 research, ensuring that the results captured feedback across genders. No dedicated mentorship or gender support programmes were applied within WP4.

Work Package 5:

In the 1st audit, WP5 identified the underrepresentation of women in technical and engineering roles as its main gender-related challenge. To address this, WP5 set recruitment targets for women in both research teams and leadership positions, aiming to ensure balanced participation. It also encouraged equal participation of all genders in decision-making processes, which were already broadly inclusive. Gender considerations were integrated into the research design by assessing how findings might impact diverse groups, while an internal mentorship programme was introduced where senior female researchers supported early-career women and other underrepresented genders. Planned actions included refining hiring and promotion policies to raise female representation in leadership to at least 50% and continuing the internal mentorship programme.

By the 2nd audit, WP5 maintained continuity in gender balance, with no changes in team composition. Representation remained stable across both research and decision-making processes, applying the same inclusive approach as previously. The mentorship programme continued to be applied within WP5, though no further refinements were made to methodologies during this stage.

Work Package 6:

In the 1st audit, WP6, coordinated by GOBCAN-ACIISI, was reported as well-balanced, with its core team composed of one male and one female, and supported by CE where the project manager is female. All partners contributed staff to WP6 activities, and each organisation had representation in the Steering Committee, ensuring fair and inclusive decision-making. WP6 also included a dedicated task (6.7) on gender equality and diversity, which developed guidelines and promoted synergies with other EU projects such as ATHENA and WINDBLUE. These efforts aimed to strengthen awareness and adoption of equality and diversity principles across the consortium. Planned actions included finalising the guidelines and delivering D6.5, the formal report on Gender Equality and Diversity Principles, by month 36.

By the 2nd audit, WP6 reinforced its commitment by promoting the engagement of female scientists and technicians across project activities. Several initiatives were carried out, including a communication campaign highlighting female experts in AquaWind to mark the International Day of Girls and Women in Science. Task 6.7 also led a survey across partners to assess good practices on gender and diversity, the results of which were summarised in Deliverable D6.5, submitted in August 2025. The same balanced approach in leadership and decision-making was maintained, with WP6 continuing to support partners through guidelines, campaigns, and dedicated actions.

Work Package 7:

During the 1st audit, WP7 established balanced participation across partners, supported gender-sensitive communication, and embedded gender and diversity principles in the Dissemination & Communication Plan. It also promoted synergies with other EU projects (ATHENA, WINDBLUE) and supported partners in adopting inclusive language. F

On the other hand, 2nd audit, WP7 consolidated these efforts, promoting gender-sensitive language in all communications and raising awareness of diversity principles through campaigns such as the International Day of Girls and Women in Science. Overall, WP7 evolved from setting rules and procedures to actively implementing awareness-raising initiatives and providing visible support across the consortium.

3.3. ETHICS – RESEARCH INTEGRITY

Ethics and Research Integrity (ERI) have been embedded in AQUAWIND as a guiding principle to ensure that all activities align with Horizon Europe standards and national regulations. Across the work packages, the audits show clear progress in consolidating transparency, accountability, and responsible practices from the 1st to the 2nd period.

Work Package 1:

In the 1st audit, an internal ethics committee was established to review deliverables, ensuring compliance with standards on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. Transparency was promoted by documenting research methodologies and making results publicly available through open-access channels.

By the 2nd audit, these practices were further reinforced. WP1 continued internal ethics reviews, conducted targeted training on ethics and gender-related risks, and ensured

compliance with project-wide ethical principles. However, planned methodology guidelines for greater transparency were not fully developed in this period, highlighting an area for improvement. Overall, WP1 maintained strong ethical oversight while identifying the need for more structured guidance on methodology reporting.

Work Package 2:

In the 1st audit, WP2 confirmed compliance with EU standards and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including GDPR requirements. Ethical considerations covered environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent, supported by a Data Management Plan for handling sensitive data. The EnerOcean teams were trained in ethical compliance, with oversight from the Project Steering Committee to review deliverables for adherence to ethical guidelines on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. Transparency was ensured by documenting methodologies, providing open-access information, and submitting continuous reports to the European Commission.

In the 2nd audit, all WP2 deliverables had been finalized and submitted, leaving no additional planned actions during this period. While no new developments were reported, the earlier practices established in the 1st audit ensured that ethical compliance and transparency were upheld across WP2 activities.

Work Package 3:

In the 1st audit, WP3 confirmed adherence to EU ethical standards, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR, with a Data Management Plan guiding sensitive data handling, stakeholder engagement, and IP issues. The Steering Committee (SC) oversaw ethical compliance, reviewing all deliverables to ensure alignment with data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement requirements. For biological testing, procedures followed the EU Directive (2010/63/EU) on animal welfare, with protocols approved by the Bioethical Committee of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Transparency was maintained through regular updates to partners and the SC, and deliverables were prepared for submission to the EC, including plans for scientific publications and dissemination.

In the 2nd audit, WP3 had finalized its activities, with all deliverables submitted. While no new tasks were planned, the team ensured that scientific publications respected EU ethics and data protection standards. Reporting to the EC was maintained, and efforts continued on open-access publications and dissemination within the consortium and external networks.

Work Package 4:

During the 1st audit, WP4 reported strong adherence to EU standards and regulations, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. A Data Management Plan was in place to guide ethical management of sensitive data, participant engagement, and IP issues. The Steering Committee (SC) oversaw compliance, ensuring that deliverables met ethical requirements, particularly regarding data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. Planned actions included periodic reviews, compliance checks, and preparation for biological tests under the EU Directive on animal welfare, with approval by the Bioethical Committee of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Transparency was supported through regular updates to the consortium, with deliverables and reporting to the European Commission planned.

During the 2nd reporting period, WP4 continued to implement ethics and data management standards in the pilot demonstration activities. The Data Management Plan remained relevant and ensured proper handling of sensitive data and ethical compliance. Due to technical delays and regulatory bottlenecks, some deliverables were postponed, with finalization expected after the ongoing demonstration phase. Nevertheless, ethical oversight was maintained, and all results will undergo review before submission to the consortium and the European Commission.

Work Package 5:

During the 1st audit, an internal ethics committee was established to review deliverables, ensuring compliance with data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. Transparency was promoted by documenting methodologies and data collection processes, making results available through reports and scientific publications in line with open-access policies. Planned improvements included the introduction of pre-submission ethics audits and the preparation of methodology guides to enhance replicability.

In the 2nd audit, WP5 reinforced this framework by delivering training sessions on ethics and gender equality, with a focus on gender-related risks. Internal ethics reviews continued to ensure compliance across deliverables. While the planned methodology guidelines were not fully developed during this phase, transparency was upheld through ongoing publication of results and adherence to open-access practices. WP5 therefore demonstrates continuity in ethical compliance, while still needing to consolidate improvements in methodology guidance and structured audits for future implementation.

Work Package 6:

During the 1st audit, WP6 ensured that the Data Management Plan was in place and periodically reviewed, supporting partners in managing activities that involved personal data or external stakeholders. Ethical compliance was monitored through the Steering Committee (SC), with responsibilities shared by the Project Coordinator and Management Board. Deliverables and outputs were systematically reviewed to ensure alignment with data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement requirements. Transparency was supported by open-access publications, reports, and continuous reporting to the European Commission.

In the 2nd audit, WP6 reinforced this framework by ensuring the correct implementation of research activities, particularly in the handling of sensitive data. The SC continued to review deliverables and progress, guaranteeing partner representation and open decision-making processes. Regular online meetings ensured active communication among partners, supporting both ethics compliance and data management practices. Transparency measures remained valid and effective, with documentation of methodologies and results continuing to be openly available. Overall, WP6 demonstrated continuity in applying strong ethical oversight, maintaining GDPR compliance, and ensuring transparent and inclusive research processes.

Work Package 7:

In the 1st audit, WP7 supported partners in ensuring compliance with ethical standards, especially when handling external-facing activities such as events and newsletters. Deliverables were reviewed by the Steering Committee (SC) to guarantee alignment with ethical principles, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. WP7 also promoted transparency by making public deliverables available through diverse communication channels and ensuring regular reporting to the European Commission.

During the 2nd audit, WP7 continued to ensure GDPR compliance and supported partners in applying ethics and data management measures in dissemination to external audiences. The SC maintained its role in reviewing WP7 deliverables and actions, confirming compliance with ethics and data management requirements. Transparency practices remained consistent, with open access to public deliverables and systematic reporting maintained throughout the period. Overall, WP7 demonstrated continuity in managing ethics in dissemination while ensuring transparency, accountability, and alignment with EU ethical frameworks.

3.4. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Stakeholder Engagement (SE) has been a central pillar of AquaWind's RRI strategy, ensuring that perspectives from academia, industry, government, and society are systematically incorporated into the project. Progress from the 1st to the 2nd audit shows a shift from mapping and initial identification of relevant actors toward more structured, inclusive, and participatory engagement. It is worth highlighting that a specific task on stakeholder engagement is included in WP1. Recent D1.4 also builds on the activities implemented under this task and provides overall recommendations for stakeholder engagements in multi-use projects.

Work Package 1:

In the 1st audit, WP1, led by PLOCAN, actively engaged quadruple helix stakeholders (academia, industry, government, and civil society) through workshops, conferences, and public consultations. Local community organizations were also involved via outreach programs, field visits, and participatory workshops, ensuring that their perspectives were integrated into AquaWind's research process. Online engagement was supported through LinkedIn, Twitter, and a dedicated AquaWind website to disseminate updates, research findings, and multimedia content. Plans were made to continue these activities and further enhance the project's online presence in line with the public engagement plan.

In the 2nd audit, WP1 continued to implement its stakeholder engagement plan, reinforcing connections with the quadruple helix actors and maintaining its collaboration with local communities. AquaWind participated in FIMAR, which offered opportunities to interact with the public and raise awareness of the project's objectives. Online dissemination efforts were maintained through the established communication channels, ensuring continuity of engagement and visibility of project outcomes.

Work Package 2:

In the 1st audit, WP2 contributed to stakeholder engagement primarily by informing WP7 and Task 1.4 about its core activities and results, ensuring dissemination to quadruple helix stakeholders. A survey promoted under Task 1.4 assessed the perception of multi-use pilot projects, providing valuable feedback for future engagement. WP2 also engaged through conference posters, abstracts, participation in events, collaborations with experts and service providers, and contributions to dissemination and communication actions led by WP7. Plans were established to

continue sharing results via scientific publications, events, and close coordination with WP7 activities.

In the 2nd audit, WP2 further consolidated its engagement with stakeholders. Non-IP-sensitive activities were actively shared through project dissemination actions, including dedicated events such as the AquaWind Showcase. Coordination with WP7 was reinforced, with WP2 providing inputs for media campaigns, promotional videos, and event participation to expand outreach. Technical details remained partially undisclosed due to IP protection, but the WP maintained strong involvement in open events and communication activities to ensure stakeholder visibility and participation.

Work Package 3:

In the 1st audit, WP3 engaged with quadruple helix stakeholders by closely coordinating with WP7 and Task 1.4 to disseminate its core activities and results. A survey promoted under Task 1.4 helped assess the perception of aquaculture in multi-use contexts, which was directly relevant to WP3. In addition, WP3 engaged stakeholders such as experts, policymakers, and service providers in specific technical activities. At the local level, WP3 contributed through conference posters, abstracts, participation in events, supervision of master's theses, and collaborations with specialised providers, alongside cooperation with dissemination and communication actions from WP7. In particular, the WP promoted two final degree study works in 2025:

- [Puesta en marcha y validación de prototipo de jaula de cultivo offshore para integración en una plataforma multiusos: Ensayo biológico con especie modelo Dorada \(*Sparus aurata*\). | accedaCRIS](#)
- [Analysis of the colonization of marine biota in ocean cages | accedaCRIS](#)

In the 2nd audit, WP3 consolidated these actions by continuing to focus on sharing relevant results publicly. Coordination with WP7 ensured that WP3 contributions were included in events, the final conference (scheduled towards the project's closing phase), and digital dissemination channels. Stakeholder engagement was therefore broadened, ensuring that results were accessible to different audiences beyond the project.

Work Package 4:

In the 1st audit, WP4 reported engagement with quadruple helix stakeholders through cooperation with WP7 and Task 1.4, which conducted surveys on the perception of multi-use pilot projects. Additional involvement included experts, policymakers, and external providers linked to technical activities. Strategies included conference posters, event participation, and collaboration with experts and service providers. Also, a training

session with university students (from the Board of EU Students of Technology) was ensured. For the next phase, WP4 planned to focus on executing test pilots, collecting data for evaluation, and preparing relevant public deliverables, with results to be made public (non-IP sensitive).

By the 2nd audit, WP4 was still in the implementation phase of test pilots, but progress and interim results were already being shared through events and digital channels. Moreover, the WP team promoted an additional training session, this time with students from the University of Las Palmas, namely from the Master's Degree in Marine Crops. This overall approach is expected to continue for the remainder of the project. Furthermore, scientific publications are planned to disseminate the final results of WP4 testing, ensuring stakeholder engagement and transparency.

Work Package 5:

During the 1st audit, WP5, led by PLOCAN, actively engaged quadruple helix stakeholders (academia, industry, government, and civil society) through workshops, conferences, and public consultations. Local community involvement was fostered via outreach programs, field visits, and participatory workshops to ensure integration of perspectives. WP5 also used online platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and the AquaWind website to share research updates and multimedia content. Planned actions included continuing stakeholder engagement and strengthening online presence in line with the public engagement management plan.

By the 2nd audit, WP5 had continued the engagement plan, maintained local community involvement and offered opportunities to interact with the public (e.g., during FIMAR). Online dissemination activities also advanced, ensuring consistent visibility of project results through social media and the AquaWind website. WP5 thus consolidated its role in structuring and expanding stakeholder engagement, from local communities to broader public audiences.

Work Package 6:

The 1st audit, focused on project management and internal coordination, ensuring correct communication and reporting of project activities. It worked in close cooperation with WP7 on dissemination and communication with the quadruple helix. Task 6.5 (data management plan) ensured that public results were made available online and shared with the European Commission and stakeholders, while Task 6.7 organised awareness-raising activities on gender equality in research. WP6 also cooperated with WP1 and WP7 to involve community organisations and stakeholders, with public deliverables disseminated to reach relevant groups. Results were promoted through the

project website, Zenodo, and additional dissemination channels managed by WP7 and WP1.

During 2nd audit maintained good cooperation and communication with WP7, guaranteeing that public results were widely shared with external audiences to support sustainability and replication. Collaboration with WP1 and WP7 continued, delivering new actions for stakeholders, events, and the promotion of public, non-sensitive project information. Public deliverables and open-access results were correctly promoted and monitored, ensuring transparency and stakeholder engagement throughout the period.

Work Package 7:

In the 1st audit, dedicated strategies and tools for each stakeholder group were defined in its Dissemination & Communication (D&C) Plan, approved by the EC. It performed regular evaluations and reports to refine the strategy. Engagement relied strongly on digital channels (project website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and online events), complemented by onsite activities. WP7 also supported a WP1 survey and contributed to EU Policy Feedback Reports. At local level, WP7 ensured participation in events, fairs, conferences, and meetings with policymakers. An onsite project meeting was held in Gran Canaria (March 2024) with site visits and participation of EU and regional representatives. Each partner contributed to local dissemination through their own channels. WP7's core digital platform, the AquaWind website, was regularly updated with news, events, and project results, while LinkedIn and Zenodo were used to engage a broader audience and share open-access datasets.

During 2nd audit, it continued to implement diverse communication and dissemination activities, both digital (website, social media, newsletters, videos, press releases) and face-to-face. In June 2025, WP7 co-organised with WP5 a Project Showcase Event, open to quadruple helix stakeholders and especially targeting potential investors. Dissemination actions were reinforced through strong cooperation with Task 1.4, ensuring close monitoring and follow-up of partners' activities. Both digital and in-person channels were used extensively to promote results and engage stakeholders. The approach to online platforms remained valid and effective, with continuous updates and periodic monitoring ensuring wide outreach.

3.5. SCIENCE EDUCATION

Science Education (SEd) has been a cross-cutting component of AQUAWIND's RRI approach, aimed at raising awareness of multi-use offshore platforms and fostering public understanding of renewable energy and aquaculture integration. The two audits reflect progress from early awareness-raising activities to more structured dissemination and training initiatives.

Work Package 1:

During the 1st audit, WP1 contributed to promoting STEM education by collaborating with schools and universities to encourage careers in oceanography and renewable energy. Although no AquaWind-specific educational materials had been developed at that stage, PLOCAN actively participated in science fairs, conferences, and educational webinars, and also hosted open days at research facilities to engage students and the general public. Planned actions included expanding this collaboration to integrate blue economy projects into STEM education and developing educational materials based on technical reports, particularly in health and safety. No specific training initiatives for students or early-career researchers were foreseen.

By the 2nd audit, WP1 had reinforced these efforts by collaborating with schools through two dedicated programs, **EDUSEN and EDUBLUE**, aimed at high school students. These programs promoted knowledge of renewable energy technologies, including solar, wind, and hydrogen production. While no AquaWind-specific educational materials were produced, WP1's participation in **FIMAR**, a local fair showcasing marine and harbour economy initiatives in Gran Canaria, provided opportunities for broader community engagement. Training initiatives for students or early-career researchers remained not applicable.

Work Package 2:

During the 1st audit, WP2's role in STEM education was indirect, since it was not a core action of the work package. However, WP2 supported WP7 dissemination activities whenever relevant, ensuring STEM aspects were included. Project promotional materials such as newsletters, videos, abstracts, and deliverables were produced, although no specific AquaWind-based educational resources were foreseen in the grant agreement. WP2 also contributed to science education initiatives by supporting WP7 in events for civil society and the research community, with results documented in deliverables D7.5 and D7.6. Planned actions focused on continuing to support D&C

efforts and ensuring that public information integrated into deliverables could later serve as educational material.

By the 2nd audit, WP2 had maintained this supportive role, assisting other WPs in dissemination activities that contributed to STEM education. Public information contained in project deliverables continued to serve as a potential resource for future research and educational purposes. WP2 also provided feedback and input to WP7 dissemination actions, notably in media campaigns and the organisation of the **Showcase Event**, thereby ensuring AquaWind's results were communicated to a wider audience.

Work Package 3:

During the 1st audit, contributed to promoting STEM education mainly through collaboration with WP7's dissemination and communication actions, including the BEST Initiative training and the BlueUP Hackathon, which introduced the project and engaged students in renewable energy and aquaculture themes. WP3 further supported STEM education by providing technical insights into aquaculture systems, which were made accessible to students and the public. Notably, a master's thesis was also developed based on WP3 activities. Although no dedicated educational materials were created under WP3, promotional outputs such as videos, newsletters, abstracts, and presentations were disseminated. WP3 also supported WP7 in science education events targeting civil society and the research community and participated in training activities to raise awareness of multi-use research projects within the blue economy. Planned activities included evaluating the potential for developing dedicated educational resources (e.g., ULPGC outputs) and continuing to support dissemination and communication actions.

By the 2nd audit, continued to collaborate with dissemination and communication actions to ensure that relevant aquaculture results were promoted for STEM education purposes. WP3 actively supported science education through the promotion of two final degree studies and the participation in public events such as the AquaWind project Showcase in June 2025, EU Maritime Days in Cork, FIMAR in Las Palmas, and the Turquoise X Summit in Lanzarote. These events allowed WP3 to share outcomes with both students and the broader public, consolidating its role in linking technical results to STEM promotion.

Work Package 4:

During the 1st audit, WP4 contributed indirectly to STEM education through dissemination and communication activities, such as the BEST Initiative training and the

BlueUP Hackathon, providing technical information on the AquaWind pilots and expected results. This allowed planned outputs to be shared with students and the public. Project promotional materials, including videos, newsletters, abstracts, and presentations, were produced, but no specific WP4-branded educational materials were foreseen at that stage. WP4 supported WP7 in science education initiatives and was also involved in awareness-raising sessions with BEST students, highlighting multi-use projects and careers in aquaculture, engineering, and biology. Planned activities included continuing to support dissemination and communication actions and leveraging public deliverables as educational resources for further research.

By the 2nd audit, WP4 maintained this role, ensuring relevant pilot-related knowledge was integrated into STEM education promotion when appropriate. **A training and field visit was organised with students of the UPGC master's degree in Marine Crops.** WP4 further maintained its participation in WP7 awareness-raising activities through dissemination in major events.

Work Package 5:

During the 1st audit, collaboration with schools and universities were performed to promote careers in oceanography and renewable energy, laying the basis for STEM outreach. No AquaWind-specific educational materials had been produced yet, but there were plans to create resources based on technical reports. WP5 also participated in science fairs, conferences, and educational webinars, as well as hosting open days at research facilities to engage students and the public. The main objective for the following period was to expand collaboration by integrating blue economy projects and continuing PLOCAN's involvement in science education events.

By the 2nd audit, WP5 had continued this collaboration through programs such as **EDUSEN and EDUBLUE**, engaging high school students on renewable energy topics (solar, wind, hydrogen). However, no AquaWind-specific educational materials were developed during this phase. WP5 maintained active participation in science education events, notably through its involvement in **FIMAR**, a local fair in Gran Canaria that connects marine and harbour economy stakeholders.

Work Package 6:

In the 1st audit, WP6's role in STEM education was indirect, since its focus is project management and coordination. Instead of producing educational content, WP6 ensured that other WPs could contribute to science education effectively by maintaining high-quality management of activities. Educational and promotional outputs such as videos, newsletters, and abstracts were developed at project level, but no specific WP6-led

materials were foreseen. Its contribution to science education relied on coordination with WP7 and WP1 (Task 1.4). Planned actions for the following period included continuing to support other WPs in ensuring coherence and quality in their science education activities.

By the 1st audit, WP6 continued this role, safeguarding proper management mechanisms for project activities and partner cooperation. As expected, WP6 did not generate standalone educational materials or lead direct science education initiatives, with these activities remaining under WP7's scope. Instead, WP6 provided structural support, ensuring that AquaWind's science education actions—particularly those led by WP7—were efficiently implemented and aligned with project objectives.

Work Package 7:

During the 1st audit, WP7 contributed to STEM education mainly through its dissemination and communication activities, promoting student involvement in initiatives such as the **BEST Initiative training** and the **BlueUP Hackathon**, which served to introduce young audiences to blue economy careers and inspire interest in STEM. Along WP7 timespan, public events such as FIMAR were coordinated, ensuring visibility of the project among civil society and young people. Promotional outputs were developed at project level, including videos, newsletters, abstracts, and presentations, while plans were made to assess the potential for producing additional materials or supporting other WPs with dedicated educational resources.

By the 2nd audit, science education dimension was enhanced, with activities including AquaWind's participation in FIMAR 2025 and preparation for student engagement at the BlueUP Hackathon in autumn 2025. Additional promotional materials such as videos and flyers were produced and shared across national and international events. Science education involvement continued, building on the same approach as the 1st audit, while new training and awareness-raising actions were supported through events like the **Project Showcase Event in June 2025**, the consortium, also committed to continue supporting student-focused initiatives until the end of the project, reinforcing its role in bridging AquaWind with younger generations and educational communities.

4. Conclusion

The implementation of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles in AquaWind has been systematically monitored during the two reporting periods through the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT), completed by all Work Package (WP) leaders. This process provided structured input on five key dimensions — Open Access, Gender Equality, Ethics and Research Integrity, Stakeholder Engagement, and Science Education — enabling the consortium to measure progress, identify gaps, and adopt corrective measures when required.

1st Audit (1 September 2022 – 31 October 2024)

The 1st audit established the baseline for RRI integration across the consortium:

- **Open Access:** Internal sharing practices and compliance procedures were set up, with initial steps taken towards FAIR alignment, though further efforts on data standardisation and metadata were needed.
- **Gender Equality:** Balanced participation was observed, with female leadership roles present, but gender perspectives had not yet been systematically integrated into methodologies.
- **Ethics and Research Integrity:** Consistent compliance with Horizon Europe standards and the European Code of Conduct was demonstrated, although harmonisation of practices across WPs required reinforcement.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Initial mapping and networks were developed with quadruple helix actors, but feedback mechanisms and systematic dialogue were still at an early stage.
- **Science Education:** 1st steps were launched through awareness activities and early outreach, highlighting the need for structured educational resources.

Overall, the 1st audit confirmed that RRI principles were embedded from the outset, laying the foundation for stronger integration in subsequent phases.

2nd Audit (1 November 2024 – 1 August 2025)

The following audit demonstrated consolidation of practices and clear progress on earlier recommendations:

- **Open Access:** Deliverables and datasets began to be prepared for publication in repositories, adopting harmonised formats and metadata, thus improving accessibility and reusability.
- **Gender Equality:** Female participation was maintained, and visibility of women's contributions improved through dissemination and stakeholder processes.
- **Ethics and Research Integrity:** Partners continued to integrate ethical oversight into planning stages, ensuring traceability of results, compliance in stakeholder engagement, and alignment with data protection.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engagement became more structured, inclusive, and directly linked to technical validation, environmental assessments, and exploitation planning.
- **Science Education:** Outputs matured into more comprehensive educational actions, including final degree theses, a master's degree thesis, trainings with university students, targeting the next generation of Blue Economy professionals.

This final audit confirms a positive trajectory in RRI implementation. AquaWind has moved from establishing compliance and baseline practices to actively integrating inclusivity, transparency, and openness into project activities. Going forward, for the last phase of the project, emphasis should remain on finalising data releases under FAIR principles, consolidating gender-sensitive approaches, and ensuring stakeholder feedback informs final outputs — strengthening the project's long-term societal and scientific impact.

ANEXES

4.1. Open Access

WP1

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	Aim to publish findings in open journals	For the next phase, we aim to increase this to 75%, aligning with AQUAWIND's open-access policy.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	All public deliverables and datasets related Currently, deliverables from WP1 are	PLOCAN expects to make available to all partners the DAP (Detailed Action Plan)
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	We ensure accessibility by uploading datasets and related documentation to recognized repositories like Zenodo, and all publications have DOIs for easy tracking.	Continue uploading databases
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	We have a comprehensive data management plan that outlines open-access provisions, detailing how and when data is released.	The plan will be updated to include provisions for future data types generated in WP1 ensuring they comply with FAIR

WP2

<p>What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?</p>	<p>WP2 deals with the upgrade of the w2Power 1.6 prototype to the aquaculture version, the logistics required for sea trials and the installation of the aquaculture equipment. Although some parts of this WP are sensitive due to intellectual property issues, a part of the data and results will be made available in peer-reviewed open access publications, especially the results related to the new designs implemented. It should also be mentioned that the first activities and results of WP2 have already been presented in the form of conference</p>	<p>Work planned for the next year is to continuously ensure sharing of public data and coordinate with WP7 to ensure dissemination and exploitation when relevant.</p>
<p>Which elements of your WP are Open Access?</p>	<p>All deliverables from WP2 are sensitive, thus they will not be shared with the public. However, part of the information will be published in peer-reviewed publications / conference posters/abstracts. General design and testing information will feed project</p>	<p>The next step is to keep evaluating which data is not IP-sensitive and can be shared with the public and made available for further research via open-access scientific publications, however public dissemination of relevant information has been performed in</p>
<p>How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?</p>	<p>Through scientific publications and conference posters/abstracts and by sharing non-IP-sensitive information to WP7 for dissemination purposes. Also, WP2 activities are presented in events/conferences</p>	<p>The next step is to continue working on the same approach.</p>
<p>Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?</p>	<p>WP2, as the other WPs of the project, refers to WP6 Data Management Plan and coordinates with Task 6.5 when dealing with data management.</p>	<p>The next step is to periodically revise the data management plan in order to understand whether new datasets are needed to be added to the report or there is the need to update any of the existing ones.</p>

WP3

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	WP3 deals with the AquaWind aquaculture prototype, including the design of the aquaculture system and the harbourside aquaculture trials. Although some parts of this WP (and corresponding deliverables – D3.1, 3.2, 3.3) are sensitive due to IP issues, a portion of data and results will be made available in open-access peer-reviewed publications, especially results related to the harbourside trials. It must be also mentioned that first WP3 activities and results have already been presented in conference posters/abstracts, particularly in the Spanish National Aquaculture Congress 2024. Also, a master's thesis has stemmed from WP3 work.	Work planned for the next year of the project relates to the preparation of a number of scientific publications to present key results emerged from the development and testing phases of WP3. A peer Q1 publication, reporting D3.3 results would be prepared within next months
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	All deliverables from WP3 are sensitive, thus they will not be shared with the public. However, part of the information will be published in peer-reviewed publications / conference posters/abstracts. General design and testing information will feed project communication actions such as newsletters.	The next step is to keep evaluating which data is not IP-sensitive and can be shared with the public and made available for further research via open-access scientific publications.
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	Through scientific publications and conference posters/abstracts and by sharing non IP-sensitive information to WP7 for dissemination purposes. Also, WP3 activities are presented in events/conferences. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that a master's thesis within ULPGC has been prepared based WP3 work.	Continue to evaluate which information from WP3 is suitable for public sharing and through which means and channels. In particular, as stated before, relevant scientific publications are in the pipeline.
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	WP3, as the other WPs of the project, refers to WP6 Data Management Plan and coordinates with Task 6.5 when dealing with data management. WP3, when relevant, follows GDPR rules in terms of data privacy and protection.	Continue to refer to WP6 Data Management Plan and assess if relevant updates are needed with regards to WP3. Cooperate with the Project Coordinator and other relevant WP leaders if doubts or issues in terms of data protection arise for WP3.

WP4

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	WP4 deals with the demonstration pilots of the AquaWind multi-use prototype (aqua+wind). Although some parts of this WP (and corresponding deliverable D4.1) are sensitive due to IP issues, results from the testing and evaluation of impacts are expected to be made available in open-access peer-reviewed publications and will be presented in dedicated events and conferences, such as the project Final Conference. Moreover, deliverables D4.2, 4.3, 4.4 are public and will be shared open-access upon EC approval.	Work planned for the next year of the project relates to the finalisation of WP4 trials, which have just begun and, based on the results obtained, WP4 team will work on scientific publications and dissemination in events/conferences as well as on the public deliverables D4.2, 4.3, 4.4.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	Three out of four deliverables from WP4 are public and, upon EC approval, they will be shared on the project website and open-access platforms like Zenodo as other project public deliverables.	The next step is to keep evaluating which data is not IP-sensitive and can be shared with the public and made available for further research via open-access scientific publications / deliverables. WP4 team will consider relevant publications and conference posters/abstracts. WP4 core general outcomes will be also shared through WP7 D&C activities.
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	Through public deliverables, scientific publications and conference posters/abstracts and by sharing non IP-sensitive information to WP7 for dissemination purposes. Also, WP4 activities can be presented in events/conferences.	Upon successful execution of WP4 pilots, the plan is to draft public deliverables and to evaluate which information is suitable for public sharing and through which means and channels. In particular, as stated before, key channels could entail scientific publications, events, newsletters, press releases, etc.
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	WP4, as the other WPs of the project, refers to WP6 Data Management Plan and coordinates with Task 6.5 when dealing with data management.	Continue to refer to WP6 Data Management Plan and assess if relevant updates are needed with regards to WP4.

WP5

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	Aim to publish findings in open journals	For the next phase, we aim to increase this to 75%, aligning with AQUAWIND's open-access policy.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	All public deliverables and datasets related to V	PLOCAN expects to make available to all partners the DAP (Detailed Action Plan)
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	We ensure accessibility by uploading datasets and related documentation to recognized repositories like Zenodo, and all publications have DOIs for easy tracking.	Continue uploading databases
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	We have a comprehensive data management plan that outlines open-access provisions, detailing how and when data is released.	The plan will be updated to include provisions for future data types generated in WP1 ensuring they comply with FAIR principles.

WP6

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	WP6 is dedicated to project management and coordination. Within the WP, a dedicated task (6.5) is devoted to data management incl. the management of open-access, public data generated by the rest of the WPs. Under this task, it is ensured that public deliverables (upon EC approval) are published on the project website and relevant open-access platforms (Zenodo). Also, this task informs WP7 to ensure dissemination of those via the proper media channels. To date, all public deliverables that have been approved by the EC, have been uploaded on the AquaWind website and Zenodo.	Work planned for the next year is to continuously ensure sharing of public data and coordinate with WP7 to ensure dissemination and exploitation when relevant.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	WP6 ensures that public deliverables stemming from the other WPs are made public. If looking at WP6 deliverables per se, all are sensitive as they contain sensitive information about financial and project management reporting.	The next step is to continue to ensure sharing of relevant public data of the project and at the same time ensure that sensitive information is managed correctly according to GDPR and organisations' rules on data protection.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	WP6 ensures that public deliverables stemming from the other WPs are made public. If looking at WP6 deliverables per se, all are sensitive as they contain sensitive information about financial and project management reporting.	The next step is to continue to ensure sharing of relevant public data of the project and at the same time ensure that sensitive information is managed correctly according to GDPR and organisations' rules on data protection.
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	WP6 is responsible for coordinating with the other WPs in order to ensure that public deliverables and relevant datasets are made available on the project website and other platforms such as Zenodo.	The next step is to continue working on the same approach.
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	WP6 has established a data management plan at the beginning of the project (M6), identifying relevant WP datasets and defining key rules and procedures to ensure correct collection, processing, and sharing / storage of project data in line with GDPR. This deliverable has been submitted and approved by the EC.	The next step is to periodically revise the data management plan in order to understand whether new datasets are needed to be added to the report or there is the need to update any of the existing ones.

WP7

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	WP7 deals with communication and dissemination of the project. The WP aims to collect all relevant research public results stemming from the technical activities of the project and ensure good promotion digitally and onsite, depending on the interested target groups. WP7 includes a dedicated KPI set in the Grant Agreement for scientific publications. At the moment, the project is starting only now to generate most of the scientific data which will feed dedicated scientific publications. It must be underlined that first results were presented in conference papers/abstracts. Moreover, in cooperation with WP6, WP7 ensures that all public deliverables / datasets approved by the EC are uploaded on the	Work planned for the next year is to coordinate technical project partners from the other WPs in order to ensure the preparation of dedicated scientific publications before the end of the project. WP7 will also assess whether further poster/abstract participation is relevant in future events. Together with WP6, it will continuously ensure sharing of public deliverables/datasets on the project website and other platforms like Zenodo.
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	WP7 collects public results from the other technical WPs and give them visibility and promotion via a wide range of channels, such as project website, social media, newsletters, press releases, publications, events. Together with WP6, it ensures that public deliverables stemming from the other WPs are made public. If looking at WP7 deliverables per se, all of them are public.	The next step is to continue to ensure sharing of relevant public data, key activities and results of the project and at the same time ensure that sensitive information is managed correctly according to GDPR and organisations' rules on data protection.
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	WP7 maintains active and up-to-date the project website and social media. It periodically issues press releases and newsletters as well as organise and participate in events to share public research data. So far, the promotional efforts are summarised in deliverables D7.5 and D7.6.	The next step is to continue working on the same approach and fine-tuning the communication and dissemination approach and methods as long as new technical results are generated by the project. A large promotional campaign is foreseen in the near future to raise awareness about the pilot demonstrator of the AquaWind multi-use prototype.
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	WP7 refers to WP6 Data Management Plan and coordinates with Task 6.5 when dealing with data management. WP7 follows GDPR rules in terms of data privacy and protection.	Continue to refer to WP6 Data Management Plan and assess if relevant updates are needed with regards to WP7. Cooperate with the Project Coordinator and other relevant staff members if doubts or issues in terms of data protection arise for WP7 activities.

4.2. Gender Equality

WP1

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	The main issue is the underrepresentation of women in technical roles, especially in engineering positions within WP1	Ensure gender equality balance including PLOCAN members with different roles
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	We ensure gender balance by setting recruitment targets for women in both research teams and leadership positions.	We will review and refine our hiring and promotion policies to increase representation in leadership positions to at least 50% in the next phase.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	One issue is ensuring equal participation from all genders in decision-making discussions. Currently, most decision making discussions involve equality	Continue applying gender equality to decision making discussions
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	Gender dimension has been integrated into the research by considering how our findings may impact diverse groups differently.	We will further refine our methodologies to include gender-specific data collection and analysis, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of impacts across different gender groups.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	We have an internal mentorship program where senior female researchers mentor early-career women and other underrepresented genders in the team.	We will continue applying the internal mentorship program.

WP2

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP2 is led by EnerOcean, whose team is trained in gender equality and has an equality protocol that eliminates gender discrimination. The team is made up of men and women. In addition, EnerOcean has 50% women in the day to day management of the company and has including representation in the BoD. In the technical team devoted to this WP there are 4 women in a team of about 12 persons involved, a 33%.	Continue to ensure a fair representation of female and male project staff within WP2.
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	An issue could be related to the underrepresentation of female researchers and technicians in marine renewables and aquaculture engineering team. However, a fair balance between male and female technicians and researchers from all	Same as above.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	Same as above.
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	WP2 is highly technical, and it relates with the upgrade innovative W2Power prototype system to combine with offshore wind energy and aquaculture. Gender dimension is integrated within WP2 in the sense that different female and male technicians from project partners have been involved in WP2 activities. Although the participation is based on technical merits, women participation has been encouraged. WP2 has now finished.	Not applicable, as WP2 has just finished. However, gender dimension could be considered when producing scientific publications, when relevant.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	The Project Management Plan and the Dissemination & Communication Plan include certain recommendations and procedures in this regard.	Continue to support project partners and encourage additional actions and initiatives.

WP3

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	An issue could be related to the underrepresentation of female researchers in ULPGC aquaculture team. However, a fair balance between male and female technicians and researchers from other partners involved in WP3 has been ensured.	Not applicable. WP3 has just finished.
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as above.	Same as above.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	Same as above.
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	WP3 is highly technical, and it relates with the design, development, and initial testing of an aquaculture innovative system to combine with offshore wind energy. Gender dimension is integrated within WP3 in the sense that different female and male researchers and technicians from project partners have been involved in WP3 activities. WP3 has now finished.	Not applicable, as WP3 has just finished. However, gender dimension could be considered when producing scientific publications, when relevant.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Not applicable.	Not applicable.

WP4

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP4 is led by GOBCAN-ACIISI, whose core team is composed of one male and one female responsible managers. All project partners involve, in WP4 activities, dedicated technicians / project managers and this group seems to be well balanced.	Continue to ensure a fair representation of female and male project staff within WP4.
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as above. The Steering Committee (SC) involving all partners oversees and revises WP4 deliverables and outputs, thus ensuring a fair representation of both female and male project staff members. The SC is the decision making body of the project.	Same as above.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	Same as above.
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	WP4 is highly technical, and it relates with the testing of the multi-use prototype of the project and the assessment of results. Gender dimension can be integrated within WP4 in the sense that different female and male researchers and technicians from project partners are involved in these activities and in the production of final deliverables. Moreover, it can be mentioned that Task 1.4 foresees the promotion of a post-demonstration survey which investigates perceptions on the multi-use pilots from different stakeholder groups and female/male respondents.	Keep post-demonstration survey and deliverables.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Not applicable.	Not applicable.

WP5

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	The main issue is the underrepresentation of women in technical roles, especially in engineering positions within WP5	Ensure gender equality balance including
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	We ensure gender balance by setting recruitment targets for women in both research teams and leadership positions.	We will review and refine our hiring and
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	One issue is ensuring equal participation from all genders in decision-making discussions. Currently, most decision making discussions involve equality	Continue applying gender equality to decision
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	Gender dimension has been integrated into the research by considering how our findings may impact diverse groups differently.	We will further refine our methodologies to
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	We have an internal mentorship program where senior female researchers mentor early-career women and other underrepresented genders in the team.	We will continue applying the internal

WP6

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP6 is led by the Project Coordinator GOBCAN-ACIISI, whose core team is composed of one male and one female. GOBCAN-ACIISI is also supported by CE in certain WP6 tasks, where the project manager is female. All project partners involve, in WP6 activities, dedicated project managers and/or administrative staff and this group is well balanced. One representative from each organisation is appointed as member of the Steering Committee. These appointed persons were defined in the Project Management	Continue to ensure a fair representation of female and male project staff within WP6.
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as above.	Same as above.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	Same as above.
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	WP6 entails a task (6.7) dedicated to gender equality and diversity principles. The task aims to develop dedicated guidelines to strive for gender equality and diversity principles in the project activities and teams, as well as to promote activities/events/synergies to raise awareness of the importance of such aspects. So far, the project via WP6 promoted synergies with other EU projects focused on gender equality such as ATHENA and WINDBLIFE	Continue to promote actions and communication activities to raise awareness of gender equality and diversity principles. Finalise the guidelines and submit Deliverable 6.5 Report on adoption of Gender Equality and Diversity Principles to report on the project by M36.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Task 6.7 supports and informs the project partners about guidelines on gender equality and diversity principles. Also, the Project Management Plan and the Dissemination & Communication Plan include certain recommendations and procedures in this regard.	Continue to support project partners and foster additional actions and initiatives via task 6.7.

WP7

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP7 is led by CE, whose core team is composed of female managers. All project partners involve, in WP7 activities, dedicated project or communication managers and this group seems to be well balanced.	Continue to ensure a fair representation of female and male project staff within WP7.
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as above.	Same as above.
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	Same as above.
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	WP7 defines common rules and procedures to ensure gender and diversity principles in its communication and dissemination activities. These approaches have been set in the D&C Plan, drafted at the beginning of the project and an internal review of those is regularly performed. Moreover, WP7 team supports partners in ensuring they correctly use a gender-sensitive language in their promotional activities and publications. Finally, it is worth mentioning that WP7 works with task (6.7) to promote awareness raising actions for gender and diversity principles in research. Synergies with EU projects ATHENA and WINBLUE have been established in this sense.	Continue to ensure gender-sensitive language in communication activities of the project. Continue to support Task 6.7 to promote actions to raise awareness of gender equality and diversity principles.
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	WP7 supports and informs the project partners about gender-sensitive communication.	Continue to support project partners and foster additional actions and initiatives in cooperation with Task 6.7.

4.3. Ethics and Research Integrity

WP1

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Yes, PLOCAN team adhere to AQUAWIND's formal code of ethics, which follows the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent.	In the next phase, we plan to conduct regular training sessions on the code of ethics to ensure all team members are fully aware and compliant with its
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	We have an internal ethics committee that reviews each deliverable to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement.	We will implement a more structured
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	All research methodologies and data collection processes are documented and made available through public reports and scientific publications. Additionally, we follow open-access policies to ensure transparency in reporting.	We plan to enhance transparency by developing detailed methodology guides and making research protocols publicly available in open repositories, allowing for replication and further scrutiny by

WP2

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	AquaWind adheres to EU standards and rules on ethics, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent. In particular, GDPR is the most relevant legal framework for AquaWind, for which a Data Management Plan is in place to guide project partners in the management of sensitive data and engagement of individuals in project activities, mainly stakeholder engagement activities under	Continue to ensure fair implementation of research activities in line with EU ethics standards and ensure data protection when the involvement of sensitive data of individuals is concerned.
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The Eneercean involved teams is trained in ethical compliance to ensure European policies. Other partners has similar approaches, although maybe less formalistic. The Project Steering Committee (SC) is responsible for reviewing ethical compliance. Additionally, at WP2 level, the Project Coordinator and the Board are also responsible for ensuring the correct ethical approach of the project and supporting the consortium partners. The SC reviews each key project deliverable/result to ensure it complies with ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact and	Not applicable. All WP2 deliverables have been finalized and submitted to the consortium and the EC.
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	All research methodologies and data collection processes are documented and made available through deliverables. Open-access information, are made available by the project. The project also ensures continuous reporting to the European Commission and goes through periodic reviews to ensure quality and correctness of the activities implemented, including compliance with contracting regulations.	Not applicable. All WP2 deliverables have been finalized and submitted to the consortium and the EC.

WP3

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Aquawind adheres to EU standards and rules on ethics, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent. In particular, GDPR is the most relevant legal framework for AquaWind, for which a Data Management Plan is in place to guide project partners in the management of sensitive data and engagement of individuals in project activities, as well as management of IP issues.	Continue to ensure fair implementation of research activities in line with EU ethics standards and ensure data protection when the involvement of sensitive data of individuals is concerned. The Data Management Plan is in fact periodically revised.
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The project relies on the SC to review compliance with ethics aspects, coordinated by the Project Leader. The SC reviews each deliverable / key output of the project to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. Additionally, all the biological test and	Not applicable. All deliverables have been prepared from WP3 and submitted to the EC. However, for biological test, the procedures will be rigorously conducted according to the European Union Directive (2010/63/EU) on animal welfare protection for scientific purposes. And the experimental protocol will be approved by the Bioethical Committee of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	WP3 keeps partners and the SC updated about the progression of its activities during the project online meetings.	WP3 deliverables have all been finalised. Reporting to the EC will be ensured in the next reporting period upon needs. Partners directly involved in those scientific works conducted will be informed in advanced about the preparation of scientific publications and joint IP issues related to WP3. Those accepted for publication will be shared and disseminated throught the whole

WP4

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	AquaWind adheres to EU standards and rules on ethics, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent. In particular, GDPR is the most relevant legal framework for AquaWind, for which a Data Management Plan is in place to guide project partners in the management of sensitive data and engagement of individuals in project activities, as well as management of IP issues.	Continue to ensure fair implementation of research activities in line with EU ethics standards and ensure data protection when the involvement of sensitive data of individuals is concerned. The Data Management Plan is in fact periodically revised.
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The project relies on the SC to review compliance with ethics aspects, coordinated by the Project Coordinator. The SC reviews each deliverable / key output of the project to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement.	WP4 deliverables are foreseen for next years and will go through a review process from the SC to guarantee needed compliance. Periodic updates about WP4 will be ensured in the regular online SC meetings. However, for biological test, the procedures will be rigorously conducted according to the European Union Directive (2010/63/EU) on animal welfare protection for scientific purposes. And the experimental protocol will be approved by the Bioethical Committee of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	WP4 has periodically informed all the consortium partners and the SC about the progression of its activities during the project meetings. Deliverables will be shared with the consortium and reporting to the EU Commission (EC) is ensured.	Deliverables will be shared with the consortium and reporting to the EC will be ensured. Partners directly involved in those scientific works conducted will be informed in advanced about the preparation of scientific publications and joint IP issues related to WP3. Those accepted for publication will be shared and disseminated through the whole consortia and social networks of the

WP5

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Yes, PLOCAN team adhere to AQUAWIND's formal code of ethics, which follows the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent.	In the next phase, we plan to conduct regular
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	We have an internal ethics committee that reviews each deliverable to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement.	We will implement a more structured review
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	All research methodologies and data collection processes are documented and made available through public reports and scientific publications. Additionally, we follow open-access policies to ensure transparency in reporting.	We plan to enhance transparency by

WP6

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	AquaWind adheres to EU standards and rules on ethics, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent. In particular, GDPR is the most relevant legal framework for AquaWind, for which a Data Management Plan is in place to guide project partners in the management of sensitive data and engagement of individuals in project activities, mainly stakeholder engagement activities under WP1 and	Continue to ensure fair implementation of research activities in line with EU ethics standards and ensure data protection when the involvement of sensitive data of individuals is concerned. The Data Management Plan is in fact periodically checked at WP6 level, in order to spot the need for any updates or integrations. Partners are supported when they need to deal with activities that involve external individuals.
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The project lays on the Steering Committee (SC) to review compliance with ethics aspects. Moreover, at WP6 level, the Project Coordinator and the Management Board is also responsible for ensuring the correct ethics approach of the project and support the consortium partners. The SC reviews each deliverable/ key output of the project to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement.	WP6 Project Management Plan has defined a procedure of revision for each deliverable and other key output stemming from any WP of the project. This is also for ensuring compliance with ethics aspects, apart from ensuring quality of technical aspects. The Steering Committee (SC) is provided with the deliverable/output for review every time it is needed. Moreover, regular online meetings among the SC members ensure an open communication and sharing of information. The experience and different backgrounds of the project members involved also contribute to ensuring

<p>How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?</p>	<p>All research methodologies and data collection processes are documented and made available through deliverables, reports, scientific publications (under development). Open-access documents are made available by the project. The project also ensures continuous reporting to the European Commission and goes through periodic reviews to ensure quality and correctness of the activities</p>	<p>Maintain this approach and evaluate with the SC (or the EU) any needs for change/update.</p>
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WP7

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
<p>Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?</p>	<p>AquaWind adheres to EU standards and rules on ethics, including the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and GDPR. This code covers ethical considerations related to environmental impact, data collection, and participant consent. In particular, GDPR is the most relevant legal framework for AquaWind, for which a Data Management Plan is in place to guide project partners in the management of sensitive data and engagement of individuals in project activities, especially dissemination activities under WP7.</p>	<p>Continue to ensure fair implementation of research activities in line with EU ethics standards and ensure data protection when the involvement of sensitive data of individuals is concerned. The Data Management Plan is in fact periodically revised. WP7 also supports partners when they need to deal with dissemination activities that involve external individuals such as events.</p>
<p>What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?</p>	<p>The project relies on the Steering Committee (SC) to review compliance with ethics aspects, coordinated by the Project Leader. The SC reviews each deliverable/ key output of the project to ensure it meets ethical guidelines, focusing on data privacy, environmental impact, and community engagement. When dealing with the engagement of sensitive data from external parties such as events or newsletters, WP7 follows the procedures established in the Project Management Plan. In case of needs, WP7 refers to the Project Coordinator and the SC.</p>	<p>In WP7, next deliverables will be shared in due time with the SC members so that they can review content and ethics/data project aspects. When dealing with the engagement of sensitive data from external parties such as events or newsletters, WP7 will continue to follow the procedures established in the Project Management Plan and discuss with the Project Coordinator if there is the need for any updates.</p>
<p>How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?</p>	<p>WP7 is responsible for giving promotion of all public research data of the project employing a wide range of tools and channels, also depending on the type of stakeholder groups to reach. Public deliverables are made available. The project also ensures continuous reporting to the European Commission and goes through periodic reviews to ensure quality and correctness of the activities</p>	<p>Maintain this approach and evaluate with the SC any needs for change/update.</p>

4.4. Stakeholder Engagement

WP1

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	PLOCAN engage with quadruple helix stakeholders (academia, industry, government, and civil society) through workshops, conferences, and public consultations.	Continue the engagement plan with QH stakeholders
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	We have actively involved local community organizations through outreach programs, field visits, and participatory workshops to ensure that their perspectives are integrated into the research.	Continue to involve local community as previously done
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	We use platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and a dedicated AQUAWIND website to share updates, research findings, and multimedia content.	In the next phase, we will enhance our online pr

WP2

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	WP2 informs WP7 and Task 1.4 about core activities and results achieved for dissemination among stakeholders from the quadruple helix. Task 1.4 promoted a dedicated survey whose aim was, among others, to investigate the perception of multi-use pilot projects among stakeholders	For the next project year, mainly, WP2 will focus on sharing relevant public results and information via different channels, including scientific publications, events/conferences, and in cooperation with WP7 D&C activities.
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Conference posters/abstracts, participation in events, master's thesis, collaboration with experts and specialised service providers, and cooperation with certain D&C actions from WP7 and the Task 1.4 survey.	Publications, events, final conference, and continuous coordination with WP7 activities.
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above	See above

WP3

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	WP3 informs WP7 and Task 1.4 about core activities and results achieved for dissemination among stakeholders from the quadruple helix. Task 1.4 promoted a dedicated survey whose aim was, among others, to investigate the perception of aquaculture on stakeholders, which has been useful for WP3 too. Moreover, different stakeholders such as experts, policy makers and companies i.e., service providers have been engaged in some specific WP3 technical activities.	For the next project year, mainly, WP3 will focus on sharing relevant public results and information via different channels, including scientific publications, events/conferences, and in cooperation with WP7 D&C activities.
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Conference posters/abstracts, participation in events, master's thesis, collaboration with experts and specialised service providers, and cooperation with certain D&C actions from WP7 and the Task 1.4 survey.	Publications, events, final conference, and continuous coordination with WP7 activities.
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above	See above

WP4

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	WP4 aims to inform WP7 and Task 1.4 about core activities and results achieved for dissemination among stakeholders from the quadruple helix. Task 1.4 promoted a dedicated survey whose aim was, among others, to investigate the perception of multi-use pilot projects among stakeholders. Moreover, different stakeholders such as experts, policy makers and external providers are engaged in some specific WP4 technical activities.	For the next project year, mainly, WP4 will focus on the smooth execution of planned tests and measurements in order to collect needed data for evaluation and final assessment. Final results will be made public (non-IP sensitive ones) towards the end of the project, along with the preparation of relevant public deliverables.
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Conference posters/abstracts, participation in events, collaboration with experts and specialised service providers, and cooperation with certain D&C actions from WP7 and the Task 1.4 survey.	Publications, events, final conference, and continuous coordination with WP7 activities.
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above	See above

WP5

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	FLOCAN engage with quadruple helix stakeholders (academia, industry, government, and civil society) through workshops, conferences, and public consultations.	Continue the engagement plan with QH
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	We have actively involved local community organizations through outreach programs, field visits, and participatory workshops to ensure that their perspectives are integrated into the research.	Continue to involve local community as
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	We use platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and a dedicated AQUAWIND website to share updates, research findings, and multimedia content.	In the next phase, we will enhance our online pr

WP6

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	WP6 is focused on project management and coordination; thus, it rather deals with internal communication of partners for correct management and reporting of the project. Nevertheless, WP6 works in close cooperation with WP7 dedicated to dissemination and communication with the quadruple helix. Task 6.5 on data management plan also ensures public results are made available online and shared with the European Commission and relevant stakeholders. Task 6.7 ensures the organisation of dedicated awareness raising activities considering	Continue to ensure a close cooperation with WP7 and effective internal consortium communication and coordination in order to guarantee all activities and results of the project are met; consequently, that they can be shared with the external stakeholders and possibly replicated / uptaken.
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	WP6 cooperates with WP7 and WP1 (task 1.4 stakeholder engagement) to ensure a correct involvement of community organisations and stakeholders in the project. Public deliverables and results managed under Task 6.5 are disseminated to reach relevant	Continue to cooperate with WP7 and WP1 and assess with the consortium and relevant WP/task leaders if updates in strategies or procedures are needed.
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	WP6 publishes public deliverables and relevant datasets on the project website and open-access platforms like Zenodo. A number of additional channels are used by WP7 and WP1 to further multiply the sharing of such results with interested parties.	Continue to cooperate with WP7 and WP1 and assess with the consortium and relevant WP/task leaders if updates in strategies or procedures are needed.

WP7

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
<p>How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?</p>	<p>WP7 has defined dedicated strategies and tools for each of its stakeholder groups in the D&C Plan, submitted and approved by the EC. Periodically, WP7 performs an evaluation and report on the progression of the activities in which it refines the strategy. Shortly, digital channels are key for stakeholder engagement incl. project website, social media, online press releases & newsletters and online events. Also, WP7 contributed to the promotion of a survey from WP1 and to Policy Feedback Reports for the EU. At the same time, communication also happens offline mainly through onsite</p>	<p>Continue to implement a sound and diversified approach for communication and dissemination in order to ensure all relevant groups of stakeholders are engaged.</p>
<p>What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?</p>	<p>Strategies take place both digitally and face-to-face. At local level, the project mainly ensures participation or organisation of onsite events/conferences/fairs or meetings e.g., with policy makers in order to promote the project. Cooperation with Task 1.4 was crucial in this sense. AquaWind also held an onsite project meeting attended by the EU in Gran Canaria in March 2024, during which site visits were ensured and the engagement of key representatives from the regional government was ensured. Finally, it is worth mentioning that each project partner makes also its own contribution to local dissemination via their own established channels. Monitoring of partners' D&C activities is performed every</p>	<p>Continue to use different channels and promote events. Cooperate with Task 1.4. Monitor partners' progress with their own D&C activities.</p>
<p>How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?</p>	<p>WP7 core digital platform / window is the AquaWind website, regularly updated with news, events, and latest developments of the project. Social media platforms, especially LinkedIn, are also a key vehicle to engage with a broader audience. Open-access platforms like Zenodo are used to share public deliverables/datasets. Moreover, synergies with other projects and initiatives are sought as a way to promote AquaWind via their</p>	<p>Continue to implement this approach and periodically evaluate analytics/statistics on audience reached for relevant fine-tuning / updates.</p>

4.5. Science Education

WP1

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	We collaborate with schools and universities to promote careers in oceanography and renewable energy.	Expand this collaboration to contribute to STEM education with the integration of blue economy projects
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Educational material and resources have not been developed based on AQUAWIND	We plan to develop educational materials based on technical reports which explain the fundamentals for H&S and
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	PLOCAN participate in science fairs, conferences, and educational webinars. We've also hosted open days at research facilities, where students and the public can learn about our work.	Continue PLOCAN's participation and the organization of science fairs, conferences and educational webinars
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not Applicable	

WP2

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Although STEM education promotion is not a core action/output of the AquaWind project, this aspect is indeed considered when applicable within WP7 dissemination and communication activities.	Continue to support other WPs and ensure quality and good partners' cooperation so that activities and results are met.
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Project promotional materials were developed, along with promotional videos, newsletters, project presentations & abstracts, and deliverables. AquaWind does not foresee in its grant agreement specific educational materials. However, technical WPs might assess the relevance of producing such contents.	Public information integrated in the deliverables might be used as materials and resources for further research
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	WP2 has supported WP7 in science education initiatives, as well as events for civil society and research community. The full list of events and details on associated target groups are provided in D7.5 and D7.6.	Continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable to WP2.	Not applicable to WP2.

WP3

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Although STEM education promotion is not a core action/output of the AquaWind project, this aspect is indeed considered when applicable within WP7 dissemination and communication activities e.g., BEST Initiative training and BlueUP Hackathon to promote the project and encourage STEM education. WP3 has helped in this sense by providing relevant information on aquaculture system to be shared with the public. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that a master's thesis from ULPGC has stemmed from WP3 work.	Continue to collaborate with D&C actions of the project to share relevant WP3 results that might encourage STEM education promotion.
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Project promotional materials were developed, along with promotional videos, new newsletters, project presentations & abstracts, and deliverables. AquaWind does not foresee in its grant agreement specific educational materials. However, technical WPs might assess the relevance of producing such contents. It is worth mentioning that a master's thesis on WP3 activities by ULPGC might be considered as an educational material.	WP3 might evaluate the relevance of developing dedicated educational materials and resources, especially in the case of ULPGC which can be re-used for future university students and PhDs.
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	WP3 has supported WP7 in science education initiatives, as well as events for civil society and research community. The full list of events and details on associated target groups are provided in D7.5 and D7.6.	Continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	A training on AquaWind prototype and multi-use projects was organised with BEST students to raise awareness of the relevance of multi-use research projects in the field of blue economy, as well as to inspire young generations in careers such as aquaculture, engineering, biology. Moreover, AquaWind was disseminated among young people participating in the BlueUP Hackathon.	Continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science

WP4

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Although STEM education promotion is not a core action/output of the AquaWind project, this aspect is indeed considered when applicable within WP7 dissemination and communication activities e.g., BEST Initiative training and BlueUP Hackathon to promote the project and encourage STEM education. WP4 helps in this sense by providing relevant information on the planned pilots and expected results, which can be shared with the public.	Continue to collaborate with D&C actions of the project to share relevant WP4 results that might encourage STEM education promotion.
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Project promotional materials were developed, along with promotional videos, new newsletters, project presentations & abstracts, and deliverables. AquaWind does not foresee in its grant agreement specific educational materials. However, technical WPs might assess the relevance of producing such contents.	So far, WP4 does not plan to release any specific educational materials by the end of the project. However, public information integrated in the deliverables <u>might be used as materials and resources</u>
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	WP4 supports WP7 in science education initiatives, as well as events for civil society and research community. The full list of events and details on associated target groups are provided in D7.5 and D7.6.	Continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for – or increase awareness among – students and/or early-career researchers?	A training on AquaWind prototype and multi-use pilots was organised by WP7 with BEST students to raise awareness of the relevance of multi-use research projects in the field of blue economy, as well as to inspire young generations in careers such as aquaculture, engineering, biology. Moreover, AquaWind was disseminated among young people participating in the BlueUP Hackathon. WP4 activities were disseminated during these events.	Continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science

WP5

Questions	Year 1	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	We collaborate with schools and universities to promote careers in oceanography and renewable energy.	Expand this collaboration to contribute to STEM
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Educational material and resources have not been developed based on AQUAWIND	We plan to develop educational materials
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	PLOCAN participate in science fairs, conferences, and educational webinars. We've also hosted open days at research facilities, where students and the public can learn about our work.	Continue PLOCAN's participation and the
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not Applicable	

WP6

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	WP6 deals with project management, therefore it is not strictly and directly related to STEM education. WP6 ensures a good management of the project so that other tasks / WPs can perform this action correctly. For that, dedicated activities have been planned and executed under WP7.	Continue to support other WPs and ensure quality and good partners' cooperation so that activities and results are met.
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Not applicable to WP6. Project promotional materials were developed, along with promotional videos, newsletters, project presentations & abstracts, and deliverables. AquaWind does not foresee in its grant agreement specific educational materials. However, technical WPs might assess the relevance of producing such contents.	Not applicable.
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7 and WP1 (task 1.4).	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7 and WP1 (task 1.4).
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7.	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7.

WP7

Questions	Audit #1	
	Work conducted in past 24 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Although STEM education promotion is not a core action/output of the AquaWind project, this aspect is indeed considered when applicable within WP7 dissemination and communication activities and Task 1.4 Stakeholder engagement. In particular, AquaWind promoted its participation, through WP7, in some initiatives involving young students (BEST Initiative training and BlueUP Hackathon) to promote the project and encourage STEM education. Moreover, WP7 and Task 1.4 also ensured the participation in fairs / events such as FIMAR, where the project was promoted among civil society and	Assess the possibility of organising / taking part in additional actions for STEM education promotion.
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Project promotional materials were developed, along with promotional videos, newsletters, project presentations & abstracts, and deliverables. AquaWind does not foresee in its grant agreement specific educational materials. However, technical WPs might assess the relevance of producing such contents.	Develop additional promotional materials to share project activities and results. Support with design and communication strategy if any other the other technical WPs decide to produce dedicated educational materials based on their
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	WP7 has taken part in science education initiatives, as well as events for civil society and research community. The full list of events and details on associated target groups are provided in D7.5 and D7.6.	Continue to promote events to share AquaWind results and support science education.
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for – or increase awareness among – students and/or early-career researchers?	A training on AquaWind prototype and multi-use projects was organised with BEST students to raise awareness of the relevance of multi-use research projects in the field of blue economy, as well as to inspire young generations in careers such as aquaculture, engineering, biology. Moreover, AquaWind was disseminated among young people participating in the BlueUP Hackathon.	Assess the possibility of organising / taking part in additional similar actions.

5. Result by RRI Dimension 2nd Reporting Period

5.1. Open Access

WP1

Open Access		
Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	Findings published in zenodo	
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	Deliverables are available in Zenodo and website	
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	We ensure accessibility by uploading datasets and related documentation to recognized repositories like Zenodo, and all publications have DOIs for easy tracking.	
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	Data updated for WP1	

WP2

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?		
	Continued ensuring the share of public data and coordination with WP7.	
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	Continued de data evaluation of sensitive IP data to ensure public data publications	
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	Continued with the previous approach	
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	Continued periodic data review	

WP3

Questions	Audit #2	
Work conducted in past 12 months		
<p>What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?</p>	<p>Posters for the EU Aquaculture Congress are under development for being presented at the scientific event in September 2025. Moreover, in May 2025 an open event with university students was organised (see also WP4). In addition two final degree studies were promoted.</p>	
<p>Which elements of your WP are Open Access?</p>	<p>The project continued to evaluate data to distinguish between non IP-sensitive and IP-sensitive information.</p>	
<p>How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?</p>	<p>In this second phase of the project, WP3 finalised and has now a comprehensive overview of the data suitable for public sharing. Relevant scientific publications/posters/abstracts are under development. Sharing of key experiences and results in public events is also ensured.</p>	
<p>Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?</p>	<p>WP3 continued to refer to WP6 Data Management Plan and cooperated with WP5 to understand IP implications.</p>	

WP4

<p>What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?</p>	<p>WP4 duration has been extended and the pilots are still ongoing; therefore, once the results are collected at the end of the project, research partners involved in WP4 plan to work on scientific publications. WP4 deliverables will be also issued right before the end of the project. Finally, in cooperation with task 1.4, a final post-demonstration survey is planned to collect feedback and perceptions from the stakeholders and compare results of the pre-demonstration survey. Analysis and outcomes of the surveys are public.</p>	
<p>Which elements of your WP are Open Access?</p>	<p>WP4 has been evaluating IP-sensitive data and open-access data ready to be shared with the public through WP7 dissemination activities. It will continue to do so until the pilots are fully finalised.</p>	
<p>How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?</p>	<p>As stated before, non-IP sensitive information is shared via digital communication and events under WP7 and task 1.4 as long as the pilots run. Scientific publications are planned, along with the promotion of open-access deliverables. Sharing of key experiences and outcomes attained so far in events, such as the training with students from ULPGC Master's degree in marine crops has been promoted too.</p>	
<p>Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?</p>	<p>WP4 continues to refer to WP6 Data Management Plan and also relies on the feedback of the SC members.</p>	

WP5

Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	Findings published in zenodo	
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	Deliverables are available in Zenodo and website	
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	We ensure accessibility by uploading datasets and related documentation to recognized repositories like Zenodo, and all publications have DOIs for easy tracking.	
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	Data updated for WP1	

WP6

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?	In the last phase of the project, WP6 continued to ensure correct management and sharing of data generated by the other WPs. In particular, task 6.5 ensures correct data management including the periodic publication of public deliverables (upon approval by the EC) on channels like the website and other platforms like Zenodo. In addition, task 6.5	
Which elements of your WP are Open Access?	Same as in the previous audit.	
How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?	Same as in the previous audit.	
Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?	The data management plan was still relevant during this phase of the project including the previously identified datasets.	

WP7

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
<p>What proportion of your team's research outputs are published in open-access journals?</p>	<p>Although WP4 is still ongoing and is the WP that will mostly generate scientific data, publications and an abstract have stemmed from the WP3 results by ULPGC team in the Spanish National Aquaculture Congress: https://aquawind.eu/2024/11/05/offshore-aquaculture-a-step-towards-sustainability-and-</p>	
<p>Which elements of your WP are Open Access?</p>	<p>The same approach applied during this period fostering continuous promotion of activities and results via a variety of channels from social media & website to newsletters, video & press releases, events, and publications.</p>	
<p>How does your WP team ensure research data is accessible to the public?</p>	<p>The same approach applied in this phase too.</p>	
<p>Does your team have a data management plan that includes open access provisions?</p>	<p>The same approach was relevant for this phase too.</p>	

5.2. GENDER EQUALITY

WP1

Gender Equality		
Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	No further methodology refinements during this stage.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Continued the application of the internal mentorship program.	

WP2

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP2 activities are fully finalised. As commented in the previous audit, the WP sought to ensure - as much as possible - a fair gender balance, for instance by engaging a good representations of female members of the Steering Committee and the Management Board in the review of final results and deliverables. See D6.5 for further information on gender representation in project bodies.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as above.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as above.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	Not applicable, WP finished.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	WP2 continued to support technical activities from other WPs when relevant and provided inputs, if needed, to contribute to dissemination activities while keeping protected highly sensitive information related to IP.	

WP3

Work conducted in past 12 months		
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	Not applicable. WP3 finished.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Not applicable. WP3 finished.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Not applicable. WP3 finished.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	Not applicable. WP3 finished.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Not applicable.	

WP4

Questions	Work conducted in past 12 months	Audit #2
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	A fair representation of female/male project members within WP4 is still applicable to this last phase of the project.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as in the previous audit.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as in the previous audit.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	Same as in the previous audit.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Not applicable.	

WP5

	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Continued representation with no changes on the project team.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	No further methodology refinements during this stage.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Continued the application of the internal mentorship program.	

WP6

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	WP6 continued to promote engagement of female scientists and technicians in the project activities. It also promoted initiatives relevant to gender equality and diversity principles such as a dedicated communicational campaign on the female experts working in AquaWind to celebrate the International Day of Girls and Women in Science. Moreover, a dedicated deliverable (D6.5) reporting on actions on gender and diversity principles promoted by the project has been drafted and submitted by the	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as in the previous audit.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making	Same as in the previous audit.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	As reported above, a number of digital actions and events were promoted by task 6.7. Also, an internal survey was distributed among the project partners to assess their situation and good practices in terms of gender and diversity. All results have been summarised in D6.5.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?	Additional initiatives, as reported above, have been promoted and main outcomes summarised in D6.5.	

WP7

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and gender expertise in your WP team?	Same as in the previous audit.	
How does your team ensure gender balance in research teams and leadership positions?	Same as in the previous audit.	
What do you see as the main issues to be addressed in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness in decision-making in the team of your WP?	Same as in the previous audit.	
How is gender dimension integrated into your research design and methodology?	As previously mentioned, WP7 promoted a correct use of gender-sensitive language in internal and external communications, as well as raised awareness of gender and diversity principles through its digital channels such as the social media campaign for the International Day of Girls and Women in Science this year 2025.	
What mentorship or support programs exist for underrepresented genders in your team?		

5.3. ETHICS – RESEARCH INTEGRITY

WP1

Ethics/Research Integrity		
Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Training for ethics on gender equality. This training focused on gender associate to risk.	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	Continued with the internal reviews	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	The planned methodology guidelines we not developed during this phase	

WP2

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Continuation of fair implementation of research activities	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	Not applicable	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	Not applicable	

WP3

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	WP3 finished its activities in the last phase of the project but while producing open-access publications, it will take into account EU ethics and data protection standards.	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	Not applicable.	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	WP3 were all finalised but reporting will be ensured to the EC at the end of the project and the WP3 team is continuing its work on scientific publications.	

WP4

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Also in this period, WP4 ensured a fair overview and implementation of ethics and data management standards in the research activities that took place within the pilots. The Data Management Plan continues to be relevant.	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	WP4 deliverables are expected when the pilots are completely finalised. WP4 has gone through an extension in time due to some technical delays and bottlenecks in regulatory process. Currently, the demonstration phase is ongoing and expected to be finalised in the next	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	Information from the previous audit is still applicable.	

WP5

Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Training for ethics on gender equality. This training focused on gender associate to risk.	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	Continued with the internal reviews	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	The planned methodology guidelines we not developed during this phase	

WP6

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	Also, in this project period, the consortium and specifically WP6 ensured fair implementation of research activities and good management of data including sensitive information. The Management Plan is periodically checked and issues in this regard, discussed in project meetings when	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The SC continued to review the deliverables and, overall, the progress of the project per sé with all its research activities. Each partner is fairly represented in the Committee and counts on 1 vote for decision-making procedures. Online meetings also served to ensure close and open communication among	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	The same approach was still valid and correct during the period in question.	

WP7

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
Does your WP team have a formal code of ethics for research activities?	WP7 continued to act in line with GDPR provisions while supporting partners to deal with ethics and data management in the implementation of dissemination activities involving external audiences.	
What is the process for reviewing and ensuring compliance with ethics aspects related to your WP and deliverables?	The SC continued to review WP7 deliverables and key actions to external audiences ensuring ethics and data management compliance.	
How does your WP team maintain transparency in research methodologies and reporting?	The approach was maintained during this period too.	

5.4. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

WP1

Stakeholder Engagement	
Questions	Year 2
	Work conducted in past 12 months Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	Continued engagement plan as WP1
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Continued de local involvement giving the opportunity to engage with the general public at FIMAR
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	Continued the dissemination plan

WP2

Questions	Audit #2
	Work conducted in past 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	Non IP-sensitive activities within WP2 have been promoted in the project dissemination and communication actions and in dedicated open events such as the AquaWind Showcase Event. Most of technical details under WP2 however remain undisclosed for IP protection.
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Coordination with WP7 dissemination activities has been ensured also during this period including inputs for media campaigns, promotional video and organisations/participation in events.
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above

WP3

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	As previously planned, WP3 has been focusing on sharing relevant public results and will continue to do that beyond the project. Key outcome to mention is the achievement of two final degree studies during this second phase of audit.	
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Coordination with WP7 continued to share results in events, final conference (to be organised in the next few months), and digital channels. The open-access final degree theses were also promoted through WP7 channels.	
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above.	

WP4

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	At the moment, WP4 is still in the phase of implementing the test pilots. Final results will be made public (non-IP sensitive ones) towards the end of the project, along with the preparation of relevant public deliverables. Worth highlighting the organisation of training and field visit for university students from ULPGC Master's Degree in Marine Crops.	
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	WP4 progresses achieved so far have been shared in events and via the project's digital channels. The same approach will be followed in the remaining part of the project. In addition, scientific publications are planned with the final results of WP4 testing.	
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	See above	

WP5

Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	Continued engagement plan as WP1	
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Continued de local involvement giving the opportunity to engage with the general public at FIMAR	
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	Continued the dissemination plan	

WP6

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?	Good cooperation and communication with WP7 was ensured guaranteeing that public results are widely shared with external audiences for sustainability and replication purposes.	
What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?	Cooperation continued indeed with WP1 and WP7 to deliver new actions for stakeholders, events, and promotion of public, non-sensitive information of the project.	
How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?	Public deliverables and relevant open-access results were correctly promoted, through the coordination and monitoring WP6.	

WP7

Questions	Audit #2	
<p>How does your WP engage with the quadruple helix stakeholders to share activities and results stemming from the AquaWind research process?</p>	<p>Work conducted in past 12 months</p>	
	<p>In this period, WP7 continued to promote diverse activities to engage with stakeholders, namely: from digital communication including website, social media, press releases, newsletters, videos to organisation or participation in events to showcase the project. In coordination with WP5, a Project</p>	
<p>What strategies are used to involve community organisations and stakeholders in AquaWind research at local level?</p>	<p>A wide variety of channels have been used (see row above), both digital and face-to-face. Close cooperation with task 1.4 is ensured as well, and a periodic monitoring process is in place to follow up with partners and ensure dissemination activities at their level too.</p>	
<p>How do you use online platforms to engage with a broader audience?</p>	<p>The approach was also valid for this period and periodic monitoring ensured.</p>	

5.5. SCIENCE EDUCATION

WP1

Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Collaboration with schools with 2 programs EDUSEN and EDUBLUE. The goal of the project was to engage renewable energy (solar, wind and hydrogen production, with high school students.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	No educational materials have been developed based on AQUAWIND	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Participation in FIMAR, a local fair involving different companies around marine and harbour economy in Gran Canaria.	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable	

WP2

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	When relevant, WP2 has supported other WPs and dissemination activities contributing to promoting STEM education.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Public information integrated in the deliverables might be used as materials and resources for further research after the end of the project.	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	WP2 provided needed feedback and inputs to support WP7 dissemination actions when relevant, such as media campaigns and the organisation of the project Showcase Event.	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable to WP2.	

WP3

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	WP3 is open to continue to collaborate with D&C actions of the project to share relevant WP3 results that might encourage STEM education promotion.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Two final degree theses were achieved in this period: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Puesta en marcha y validación de prototipo de jaula de cultivo offshore para integración en una plataforma multiusos: Ensayo biológico con especie modelo Dorada (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) • Analysis of the colonization of marine biota in ocean cages 	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Also in this phase, WP3 continue to support D&C actions to promote events / initiatives to share AquaWind results and support science education such as in the Project Showcase Event organised in June 2025.	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	WP3 activities and main outcomes were promoted in further events during this period such as the EU Maritime Days in Cork, FIMAR 2025 in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the Turquoise X Summit in Lanzarote.	

WP4

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	WP4 continued to feed, when relevant, WP7 dissemination activities including actions for STEM education promotion. In this period, in fact, a training and field visit to the prototype with university students from ULPGC (Master's Degree in Marine Crops) was organised in May 2025.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Same as in the previous audit.	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Same as in the previous audit.	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Same as in the previous audit.	

WP5

Questions	Year 2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	Work planned for next 12 months
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Collaboration with schools with 2 programs EDUSEN and EDUBLUE. The goal of the project was to engage renewable energy (solar, wind and hydrogen production, with high school students.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	No educational materials have been developed based on AQUA/WIND	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Participation in FIMAR, a local fair involving different companies around marine and harbour economy in Gran Canaria.	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable	

WP6

Questions	Audit #2	
	Work conducted in past 12 months	
How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?	Also in this phase, WP6 was in charge of ensuring the correct mechanisms for high-quality management of activities and partners' cooperation.	
What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?	Not applicable.	
How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7 and WP1 (task 1.4).	
If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?	Not applicable to WP6. See WP7.	

WP7

Questions	Audit #2			
<p>How does your WP activities contribute to promoting STEM education?</p>	Work conducted in past 12 months			
	<p>Work in this phase included participation in dedicated fairs and events like FIMAR 2025 as a way to reach out to civil society and youngsters. The project plans also this autumn 2025 to promote and engage in the students' BlueUP Hackathon.</p>	<p></p>		
<p>What educational materials and resources, based on AquaWind research, have been developed and promoted within your WP?</p>	<p>Additional promotional materials like videos and flyers were ensured, along with sharing of generated knowledge in specific international and national events.</p>	<p></p>		
<p>How do your WP participate in science education events and initiatives?</p>	<p>Same as in the previous audit.</p>			
<p>If applicable, has your WP planned any initiatives to provide training about AquaWind research for - or increase awareness among - students and/or early-career researchers?</p>	<p>A Project Showcase Event was promoted in June 2025 and the consortium plans to continue to support similar initiatives like the BlueUP Hackthin until tne end of the project.</p>	<p></p>		

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